

A Simulation-Based Method of Permeability Prediction for RTM Process Simulation

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1 Introduction

Resin injection such as resin transfer molding (RTM) is commonly applied in industry for serial production of composite components. RTM process simulation enables prediction of process parameters that are essential for component and tool design. As for all simulations where material behavior is modeled, validated material properties are indispensable for realistic simulations. Currently, material properties have to be determined experimentally which is costly and time consuming. Furthermore, standardized methods for permeability testing are not yet available.

2 Overview

This paper presents an approach to predict permeability for carbon fiber fabrics based on textile models and using simulation techniques. The core idea dates back to Frishfelds et al. [1] in 2007. The most

important benefit is the speed-up compared to experimental testing. With fast material characterization, process simulation can be employed in the early design phase of a component. An optimal trade-off between component quality and producibility can be achieved without extensive prototyping and testing. The way forward is as follows: Information that is inherent in digital images of scanned fabrics is extracted using image analysis. The results are taken as input data for textile modeling in WiseTex. Then, FlowTex is employed to determine permeability. For both steps an open data exchange and scripting interface is employed [2]. A self-developed Matlab[®] routine performs the image analysis, interacts with the abovementioned tools and finally writes a material card for direct use in RTM simulation. The core idea of the method has already been published [3]. In the paper at hand crucial questions arising from the proposed method are investigated in-depth. Here, the influence of number of layers and areal weight on in-plane permeability is investigated. This is neces-

Fig.1: Data flow from digital image analysis to permeability prediction

sary since a prerequisite for the method is the optical inspection of a single layer of a fabric, but the method should be applicable for multi-layer and multi-orientation lay-ups as well. Another important step is the investigation of the robustness and effectiveness of the developed image analysis algorithms. An illustration of the method is given in Fig.1.

The major advantages of the method are the huge amount of time that can be saved compared to experimental permeability testing and the robustness of the test method.

3 Results

3.1 Study on the influence of number of layers and areal weight on in-plane permeability

The starting points for image analysis are front- and back-side scans of biaxial non-crimped fabrics. To ensure the applicability of the method for multi-layer and multi-orientation preforms an experimental study is conducted. Two non-crimped fabrics (Saertex, bi-diagonal, +45/-45) with a nominal areal weight of 274 g/m² and 540 g/m² are tested and a range of preform thickness from 1 mm to 4.8 mm has been covered. (In the following the fabrics are denoted as SAE 274 and SAE 540). The fabrics have been chosen with equal quantities (manufacturer, orientation, stitch properties) apart from the areal weight. Tests have been performed for fiber volume fractions between 50% and 56%. The results providing the relations between areal weight and number of layers are used to calibrate the numerical method.

3.2.1 Experimental setup

For the experiments a 1D permeability test setup with 4 cavities has been used, see Fig.2. An earlier version of that setup has been employed to perform the experiments for the 2nd international permeability benchmark study where high reproducibility and very good agreement with the partners that have respected the boundary condition of the Benchmark study has been achieved. Each cavity of the setup consists of an aluminum top and bottom plate. Fiber volume fraction is adjusted using metallic distance frames. With the setup unsaturated and saturated permeability can be tested without having to replace the fabric layers. The first part of an experiment is the unsaturated test where the flow front is tracked using pressure sensors. For the saturated test per-

formed right after, the flow rate is controlled using force sensors. Additionally, pressure sensors at the edge of each cavity are installed to detect - together with the flow front sensors - non-linear flow fronts which are often a hint for race tracking. Race tracking usually occurs when a little gap between lay-up and the cavity walls is left so that resin can flow much faster there than through the fabric layers.

Fig.2: 4-cavity 1D permeability test setup at LCC

3.2.2 Overview effective results

In the following, results of saturated tests are presented. A more in depth presentation including unsaturated results and single layer test will be published soon.

For each setting 5 experiments have been performed to check for the repeatability and robustness of the test method. In Fig.3 and 4 the effective permeability results for both materials are depicted. Here, values with index 0° refer to a test where the flow front progression is in the direction of the stitching (also called machining direction). Consequently, results with indices 90° and 45° arise from experiments where the fabric has been put to the mould orthogonal or in an angle of 45° compared to the 0° degree direction. In the plots, additionally the standard deviation bars are plotted which show nicely the robustness of the test method. The standard deviation for almost all configuration shows to be an order of magnitude lower than the permeability results. It can be seen that the permeability values for the SAE 274 are between 2.8 E-11 m² and 4.5 E-11 m² whereas the results of the SAE 540 are little higher and ranging between 6.3 E-11 m² and 9.9 E-11 m².

Fig.3: Effective permeability results for SAE 274 and a FVF of 51.6%

Fig.4: Effective permeability results for SAE 540 and a FVF of 50.8%

It will be shown in the following if that difference arises just from the difference in fiber volume fraction or additionally from the material. The effective results are then compiled to receive the principal permeability values (K_1 , K_2 and the rotation angle θ) using an analytical scheme proposed by Gebart et al. [4].

3.2.3 Influence of areal weight

Since the areal weight of SAE274 is not exactly the same as SAE540, both materials have been compared with a normalized fiber volume fraction of 50%. Figure 5 shows a comparison of permeability values in 0° direction for different preform thickness and normalized to 50% fiber volume fraction. The normalization has been performed by an exponential curve-fit to the permeability values over fiber volume fraction. The influence of preform thickness on the fitting parameters is very small and is not presented here in detail.

Fig.5: Effective 0° permeability results for SAE 540 and SAE 274 normalized to FVF of 50%

SAE540 shows higher permeability values for all preform thickness. The difference of permeability values over preform thickness is low for both materials. Unless, we have equal fiber volume fraction and same material type, one can observe a strong influence of the individual fiber architecture of the fabric.

3.2.4 Influence number of layers

Experiments accounting for the influence of lay-up thickness (number of layers) on permeability by keeping fiber volume fraction constant for each thickness have been performed. As can be seen in Fig.6, there is no clear trend over the thickness that can be observed for both materials (SAE274 and SAE540) and both principal directions (K_1 and K_2).

Fig.6: Principal permeability results for SAE 274 and SAE 540 over preform thickness

Further investigations for preform thickness smaller than 1.2mm will be performed

In conclusion one can state that the influence of areal weight – meaning the influence of the fabric architecture – on permeability is much more dominant than the impact of layer number - meaning preform thickness.

The rule of mixtures that is commonly applied to predict preform permeability for known ply permeability can be applied for both materials. A correction accounting for the influence of preform thickness seems to be not necessary.

3.2 Capabilities of the Image Analysis Algorithms

Six non-crimped biaxial fabrics with different orientations, varying stitch pattern / material and differences in regularity are investigated. Tab.1 gives an overview of the tested materials and Tab.2 shows fabrics' characteristics.

Name	Manufacturer	Orientation
SGL 45	SGL Kumpers	$\pm 45^\circ$
SGL 90	SGL Kumpers	$0^\circ/90^\circ$
SAE 45-1	Saertex	$\pm 45^\circ$
SAE 90	Saertex	$0^\circ/90^\circ$
SAE 45-2	Saertex	$\pm 45^\circ$
SIG 45	Sigmatex	$\pm 45^\circ$

Tab.1: Overview of tested materials

Name	Areal	Thick-	Fiber vol.
SGL 45	450 g/m ²	0.40mm	63,92%
SGL 90	449 g/m ²	0.40mm	63,78%
SAE 45-1	408 g/m ²	0.35mm	66,23%
SAE 90	406 g/m ²	0.35mm	65,91%
SAE 45-2	540 g/m ²	0.50mm	61,36%
SIG 45	300 g/m ²	0.30mm	56,82%

Tab.2: Material specifications

3.2.5 Image Processing Procedure

The image processing is exemplarily shown for the front side of material SGL 45, that can be seen in Fig. 7.

Fig.7: Scan of SGL 45 (fronstside)

The original image is segmented in its constitutive domains (fibers, gaps, stitching) using gray- level thresholding and morphological operations (e.g. erosion, filling, area opening) [5], the results can be seen Fig.8.

Fig.8: Binary image of stitch domain (left) and gap domain (right) of SGL 45

In the latter, the segmented domains are analyzed individually.

- For the fiber domain the gradients are amplified with a Canny edge detection algorithm

[6] and then a Fourier analysis [7] is employed to determine the fiber orientation. Here, number and size of the grids where the fiber orientation is evaluated can be adjusted.

- Within the analysis of the stitch domain, the stitch loops are separated using again a morphological operation (erosion) and then a Watershed algorithm [8] is employed to find the boundaries between the loops. Based on the binary images, size and aspect ratio of individual loops and orientation plus distance of the stitch line is calculated using curve-fitting.
- The analysis of the gap domain is pretty similar to the stitch analysis. An extra separation of the gaps is not necessary. Dimensions of the gaps (including aspect ratio) and orientation are determined using the same approach as for stitches.

Figure 9 shows the fiber orientation for a 9 x 10 grid. Note that the analysis is performed solely on the “fiber” pixels of the image. Gaps and stitches are depicted just for completeness. Figure 10 shows the segmentation results. The gap domain is depicted in blue color and the stitches are marked in multiple colors.

Fig.9: Analysis result of the fiber domain of SGL 45

Fig.10: Result image of SGL 45: Stitching (loops marked in colors) and gaps (marked in blue)

In the following, scans as well as results images from each of the materials in Tab. 1 are depicted showing front (top) and backside (bottom). Furthermore the images processing results are written to tables.

3.2.1 SGL 45

The distinction of the stitch domain can be nicely achieved by gray-level thresholding, just small bunches of pixels have to be cleaned morphologically. The results for the back-side are influenced by the binder content, stitching shows to be scraggy. This can be smoothed using morphological closing.

The gaps appear to be comparably small. However, the image resolution is high enough (4800dpi) that they can be segmented. The small size causes holes within the gaps which can be closed morphologically. Generally, the gap size varies in a huge range, deviations from the mean value of 120% occur. For further analysis based on unit cells, it is recommended to use mean values from a big homogenization area.

The canny image comprises mostly long edges which suits the Fourier analysis. Although, there are round and oval object, the orientation can be determined robustly. The coefficient of variation is smaller than 2.5% for front- and backside

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	45.6° (2.4%)	-44.5° (1.6%)
Gap fraction	3.8%	1.6%
Mean gap length	2.2mm	2.9mm
Aspect ratio (L/W)	10.0	10.0
Stitch fraction	10%	5.9%
Stitch length	5.1mm	5.1mm
Stitch distance	2.8mm	2.8mm

Tab.3. Analysis results for material SGL 45

Fig.11: Scan SGL 45
(top: front side, bottom: backside)

3.2.2 SGL 90

For SGL 90 segmentation of stitching works well. At the edges where stitch loops meet morphological closing has to be employed, especially for the backside. Extraction of individual loops is a little tricky for the backside. Due to the change of orientation, the seed points for water shedding have to be specified manually. This causes the loops to ‘fill’ irregularly and hence the size of the loops is calculated slightly different for each one. However, calculation of the mean value cleans that issue.

At the front side, there are two types of gaps. Firstly, there are bigger continuous channels and secondly smaller individual gaps. It is hard the segment the two types together. It is crucial to find suitable parameters for morphological operations, that the smaller gaps do not vanish. At the backside, just continuous channels can be found which is due to type of stitching. Here, segmentation of the gap domain is easier as for the front side.

The determination of the fiber orientation works robust for the front side. For the backside, however, big problems arise. The fiber bundles are quite regularly which caused the canny algorithm not to find enough edges (gradients). Secondly, the binder leads to big round and oval edges that have a huge impact on the calculated fiber orientation.

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	91.7° (2.9%)	-66.4° (28.1%)
Gap fraction	4.4%	15.7%
Mean gap length	1.8mm	6.7mm
Aspect ratio (L/W)	4.6	7.5
Stitch fraction	8.7%	8.3%
Stitch length	5.1mm	5.1mm
Stitch distance	3.8mm	6.1mm

Tab.4: Analysis results SGL 90

Fig.12. Scan SGL 90
(top: front side, bottom: backside)

3.2.3 SAE 45-1

For SAE 45-1 segmentation of stitching works well. The shapes are quite regular on both sides; just on the backside some stitch bundles are a little scraggy. This can be cleaned morphologically.

The gaps are quite small on both sides but rather regular and they have a clear triangular shape. On the front side segmentation works well. On the backside gray levels of fibers and gaps are very similar; this causes some difficulties for proper extraction.

Segmentation and analysis of the fiber domain is straightforward here. The values for front and backside as well as the low COV show that nicely.

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	44.3° (3.8%)	-45.9° (6.6%)
Gap fraction	10%	10%
Mean gap length	2.1mm	2.2mm
Aspect ratio (L/W)	11.9	7.6
Stitch fraction	12.7%	22.3%
Stitch length	5.1mm	5.1mm
Stitch distance	1.7mm	4.4mm

Tab.5: Analysis results SAE 45-1

Fig.13. Scan SAE 45-1
(top: front side, bottom: backside)

3.2.4 SAE 90

For both sides, the stitching can be clearly separated from the two other domains because of the brightness (gray-levels between 250 and 255). On the backside the endpoints of the loops have to be closed manually.

The gaps on the front side are hard to detect. At first, they are not clearly defined, a lot of filaments are crossing the gaps and the gaps are rather inhomogeneous. On the backside, the same problem occurs, but segmentation is possible.

The inhomogeneity on the front side that causes problems for the gap analysis is advantageous for the fiber orientation analysis. Here, irregularity means a lot of gradients which simplifies edge detection and Fourier transformation. On the backside bundles are very homogeneous, but orientation analysis is possible.

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	91.0° (4.3%)	-3.9° (45%)
Gap fraction	34.9%	2.9%
Mean gap length	2.6mm	1.0mm
Aspect ratio (L/W)	2.1	8.1
Stitch fraction	31.0%	16.3%
Stitch length	5.0mm	5.1mm
Stitch distance	3.2mm	6.0mm

Tab.6. Analysis results SAE 90

Fig.14: Scan SAE 90 (top: front side, bottom: backside)

3.2.5 SAE 45-2

For material SAE 45-2 an efficient image processing is possible. All methods can be applied in automatic mode and the analysis is robust, the results are of high quality (e.g. COV for fiber orientation smaller 0.6%) and are highly credible. Initially, the gray level histogram shows an almost perfect tri-modal shape, i.e. three clearly separated peaks representing the three domains. There are similarities to material SGL 45, but SAE 45-2 is without binder. So, there is no negative influence on the segmentation at all.

Based on the segmentation of the entire stitching domain, the loops can be separated easily. Even the automatic seed generation for water shedding can be employed.

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	43.0° (0.6%)	-49.6° (0.5%)
Gap fraction	4.5%	3.2%
Mean gap length	3.7mm	3.5mm
Aspect ratio (L/W)	16.6	19.8
Stitch fraction	13.6%	7.4%
Stitch length	5.1mm	5.2mm
Stitch distance	2.7mm	2.6mm

Tab.7: Analysis results SAE 45-2

Fig.15: Scan SAE 45-2
(top: front side, bottom: backside)

3.2.6 SIG 45

Material SIG 45 is very inhomogeneous which can be seen clearly at the scans. For the gray level histogram that has no influence, so segmentation should be possible. The binary images show the inhomogeneities very well gaps have different sizes and completely different shapes. The stitches show the same. This makes calculation of geometrical properties very hard. That's why this step is suspended for the analysis. The distance between the stitch lines as well as their orientation can be measured because the values are based on the mean values of the geometry of the individual stitches.

Result	Value (front)	Value (back)
Fiber orientation (COV)	52.0° (7.5%)	-52.0° (1.6)
Gap fraction	-	-
Mean gap length	-	-
Aspect ratio (L/W)	-	-
Stitch fraction	14.5%	15%
Stitch length	5.5mm	-
Stitch distance	2.3mm	-

Tab.8: Analysis results SIG 45

The algorithms prove to work robust with most of the tested fabrics and are capable of extracting all information required for textile modeling. In general, the more homogeneous a fabric is the easier is the analysis. The segmentation of the domains is always possible so that all relevant quantities for textile modeling can be approximated. Only geometric properties cannot be determined for any fabric. Due to the inhomogeneity of fabrics the question comes up how big the sample size (image size) has to be so that representative quantities can be determined. This topic will be addressed in future.

The calculation of fiber orientation is well possible and robust.

Fig.16: Scan SIG 45 (top: front side, bottom: backside)

4 Summary and Outlook

Results on both fields that have been investigated for that paper have contributed nicely to a better understanding of the presented method. Experimental results give an insight to topics where the simulation approach cannot account for by itself. Also the investigation of the image processing gave important information about its capabilities and robustness. For more realistic resin flow simulation, local preform characteristics like fiber volume fraction and shear deformation as well as their variability has to be taken into account. For that purpose image processing could be an appropriate tool. When indicated one has to rely on more elaborated method of image acquisition like e.g. CT scanning to be able to capture the entire 3D geometry.

One of the next steps is to apply the simulation approach for permeability prediction to a realistic, more complex component in order to demonstrate the benefits of the method compared to purely experimental permeability prediction. As already mentioned the topic variability will be addressed. Up to now the knowledge about required model size for representative modeling as well as the influence of fabrics' inhomogeneity is insufficient.

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